

Project Outcome

Recommendations for Open Data Practices in Visual Social Research

In Pursuit of a Code of Conduct

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1. Executive summary

In recent years, open science has gained growing importance in academia, with funding bodies, publishers, and journals increasingly encouraging, or even requiring, researchers to share their data. While such practices enhance transparency, replicability, and accessibility, they also raise significant ethical, legal, and methodological challenges, particularly in visual social research. Images, videos, and other visual materials are often highly sensitive, context-dependent, and difficult to anonymize, making generic open data guidelines insufficient for this field.

Against this backdrop, the CodeVis project (Code of Conduct for Open Data Practices in Visual Social Research), funded by the Swiss Academies of Arts and Sciences, set out to develop tailored recommendations addressing the specific challenges of visual data in open science contexts. It aims to explore how data from visual social research can be meaningfully integrated into the open data framework, focusing on the management, sharing, and reuse of visual data in ways that are ethically responsible and legally compliant, while also fostering transparency and collaboration. Rather than presenting openness as a binary choice between full publication and complete non-disclosure, these recommendations stress that decisions are rarely straightforward.

To translate these aims into practice, the project adopted a multi-step process. This involved: 1) a benchmark analysis of existing ethical codes and guidelines; 2) an extensive review of debates on visual ethics, data management, and open science; and 3) three expert workshops held between 2024 and 2025 with scholars in visual communication, media research, and the social sciences.

The outcomes of this process are summarized in the following key aspects for open data practices in visual research:

1. *Openness with responsibility*: Share visual data as open as possible, as restricted as necessary. Full openness is not automatically the default.
2. *Context sensitivity*: Adapt openness to the heterogeneous nature of visual data, considering research paradigm, and cultural, social, and methodological contexts.
3. *Ethical primacy*: ensure harm minimization, prioritizing dignity, privacy, and safety through consent, anonymization, or, where needed, textual substitution.
4. *Degrees of openness*: Apply a spectrum of sharing options, from fully open to restricted or closed, based on careful ethical, legal, and methodological evaluation.
5. *Planning ahead*: Open data practices need to be defined at the beginning of a research project within the data management plan.

Building on these principles, this document wants to support researchers in planning and implementing visual open data practices by providing guidelines on issues such as ethical and legal reflections, data management plans, consent processes, and considerations regarding repository and licensing selection. These guidelines are designed to accompany researchers throughout the data lifecycle, from project design to publication and reuse.

The value of these recommendations lies in providing the first dedicated framework for open data practices in visual social research. They offer a reliable point of reference for researchers and scholars, as well as for students and early-career academics. Ultimately, they aim to strengthen trust, enhance the rigor of visual research, and foster a culture of responsible openness that respects both academic integrity and the rights and dignity of research participants.

2. Introduction

2.1. The need for recommendations to handle visual data in open research practices

Currently, in academia, there is a movement towards open research, open data, and open science in general. With respect to open data, many international funding bodies now require data collected within publicly funded projects to be published in appropriate data repositories if there are no legal, ethical, or other reasons that might render this impossible. The same applies to many publishing houses and journals that invite or request scholars to share data used for publications, typically using data repositories.

Generally, this can be considered a positive development, fostering, e.g., transparency – by allowing readers to understand how data were created and interpreted by the authors; replicability – by enabling others to reproduce the research, either for verification or for related studies; accessibility – by providing access to research data through appropriate usage licenses – and many more. However, researchers have also emphasized the risks and ethical challenges related to open data practices, such as marginalization and potential harm to participants, thus showing that an adequate and responsible approach to open research and open data extends beyond merely making data accessible (Fox et al., 2021). It involves complex decisions with respect to promoting ethical transparency, research ethics, handling data responsibly, and reflexivity. What is considered as an “appropriate” open data approach is not necessarily a fixed, stable, or universal determination and depends, among other factors on the respective disciplines and research fields, but also on more general research paradigms, the kinds of data that are supposed to be “made open” and the implications of doing so.

We argue that *visual* social research (research focused on visual phenomena or that uses creative or visual research methods), and the data it uses or produces, yields particular challenges for open data practices. We, therefore, second the claim by Prosser et al. (2023, p. 1648) that “open science needs to be sensitive to the research, rather than the research simply adapting to open science”. Similarly, Late et al. (2024) explicitly call for guidelines that consider the unique needs of social science and humanities researchers. Accordingly, with respect to visual social research, we argue that *highlighting the unique attributes of visual data* and visual research methods, but also *providing guiding principles*, is essential as more and more research projects in the social sciences handle and analyze visual data or use visual research methods or outputs. This document thus seeks to provide some recommendations based on ethical and legal considerations applied to the field of visual social research¹.

2.2. How these recommendations have been produced

This document is based on various documents and activities. First, we conducted a benchmark analysis of existing guidelines and previous reflections on research ethics, visual ethics, open data. Documents include, e.g., the *ICA Code of Ethics* (Humphreys et al. 2019), the *Guidelines for Ethical Visual Research Methods* (Cox et al., 2014), and the recommendations by the Association of Internet Researchers’ Ethics Working Committee in *Ethical Decision-making and Internet Research* (Markham & Buchanan, 2012). We also drew on academic discussions that explore the theoretical and methodological challenges of visual communication research (Lobinger et al., 2019), as well as conceptual frameworks for integrating visual methods into the study of culture and society (Pauwels, 2020). Foundational texts in visual ethnography and visual research further enriched our benchmark (Pink, 2013), along with recent contributions

¹ Similarly, other initiatives provide practical guidance on handling visual data, such as the forthcoming *Miniguide* on open research data for photo and video. Developed as an internal guideline within HES-SO institutions for their members, it focuses on the Swiss legal context and offers concrete recommendations for managing, anonymizing, and sharing visual data—including the use of metadata to support documentation and reuse (Raubert, forthcoming).

discussing ethical challenges in open science and data practices (Fox et al., 2021; Prosser et al., 2023).

To date, there are hardly any texts and guidelines that explicitly discuss the use of visuals in open data practices. However, there is a lively discussion about ethical, legal, and pragmatic aspects of the use of images for research publications and throughout the research process in general. The arguments put forward in these debates can be transferred to some degree to questions regarding open data practices. Additionally, we considered the findings by Late et al. (2024), who discussed the challenges and ethical considerations of sharing image data based on expert interviews. Important considerations for sharing visuals can also be extrapolated from discussions about the challenges of open data practices in qualitative research (Branney et al., 2019; DuBois et al., 2018; Prosser et al., 2023).

Second, we conducted three workshops with researchers. The first involved a group of eight participants and took place in Bremen, on 20 November 2024, during the pre-conference of the Annual Conference “*Generative Images – Generative Imageries*” of the German Communication Associations’ (DGPuK) Visual Communication Division. The second involved a group of seven participants and was an online workshop held on 16 January 2025, bringing together experts in visual communication and broader communication research. The third workshop took place on 11 June 2025 during the pre-conference “*Frames of Transition: Visual Communication in Times of Social Change*” of the Visual Communication Studies Division co-sponsored by Global Communication and Social Change Division that was part of the 75th Annual Conference of the International Communication Association (ICA) in Denver. In these workshops, participants shared their expertise and raised concerns about the challenges of sharing visual data within open data practices and gave feedback on our draft documents. This document integrates the shared knowledge and feedback of the participants whom we want to thank.

Moreover, sharing visual research data also regards data management and the need to consider the whole “image lifecycle” (Fernandes et al., 2020; Rodrigues & Lopes, 2022a; Rodrigues & Lopes, 2022b). This is why we also reference some rather “technical” aspects of open data practices to highlight which decisions are essential at which points of the research process.

2.3. Goal and structure of these recommendations

These recommendations discuss how data obtained in visual social research can be meaningfully integrated into the framework of open data. This means addressing a range of considerations that influence whether and how visual research data should be collected, edited, managed, and published. Up to now, there are no guidelines and recommendations for scholars in visual social research on how to manage visual data in the context of open science.

The guidance offered here is, we hope, applicable throughout the various phases of a research project, however always with the focus on open data in mind. This includes the initial design and planning of studies involving open visual data, the preparation of dossiers for Institutional Review Committees (IRCs) and ethics boards in general, and the process of informing participants about the use of visual materials in later open data practices. We hope the recommendations are also relevant when publishing research outputs that incorporate or are accompanied by visual data, including open visual data intended for broader dissemination and reuse. By addressing these key moments in the research process, the recommendations aim to foster ethical, transparent, and responsible practices in the use of open data practices in visual social research.

Rather than presenting a binary choice between fully open publication and complete non-disclosure, these recommendations emphasize that decisions about openness are rarely clear-cut. In most cases, the decision is not a simple “yes” or “no,” but rather a blurry and context-dependent, iterative process that demands reflexivity. Researchers are invited to consider a range of intermediate options—*degrees of openness*—that balance ethical, legal, and pragmatic concerns. This flexible approach allows for tailored solutions that ideally

respect both the integrity of the research and the rights and concerns of those represented in the data or holding the rights to these data. By identifying and reflecting on the various challenges that may arise when publishing visual data, these guidelines are designed to support researchers in determining which level of openness is appropriate and feasible in each specific case.

We also hope that these recommendations will be formally recognized and endorsed by research associations in the field of visual social research. Beyond supporting individual researchers in making informed decisions, they are intended to serve as a reliable reference document for discussions with publishers, funding bodies, and institutional review boards.

2.4. What these recommendations are not

Most importantly, these recommendations pertain specifically to the *phase of sharing data* within open data practices, and not to the broader ethical and legal considerations that arise throughout the research process. In other words, these guidelines do not address research ethics in the field of visual social research as a whole. For more detailed discussions on visual ethics and visual research ethics, please refer to the relevant literature (e.g., Lomax, 2020; Papademas & The International Visual Sociology, 2009; Pauwels, 2008; Wiles et al., 2011; Wiles et al., 2012).

Moreover, we argue that, just like research ethics more broadly, recommendations concerning open data require a *sensitivity to context* (Eynon et al., 2008). Ethical research practices and principles are inherently context-specific and dynamic (Markham & Buchanan, 2012; Wiles et al., 2011; Venema et al., 2020). This means that they depend on specific research aims, methodological approaches (see also Markham, 2006; Markham et al., 2018), epistemological character, and disciplinary background. The same applies to open data recommendations. Therefore, our proposed guidelines offer suggestions in the form of key questions and considerations, rather than definitive checklists or one-size-fits-all solutions.

Similarly, these recommendations *do not constitute a legal document*. While we reference legal frameworks to illustrate certain challenges, it is important to note that legal requirements vary across countries, are dynamically updated over time, are subject to disagreement and interpretation, and must be considered accordingly.

Lastly, while we hope to provide useful guidance for researchers planning their visual open data practices, we strongly recommend that the specific procedures and rationale for making visual data available be documented in writing and submitted for *approval by an Institutional Review Board (IRB)* or the relevant research institution or organization. Ideally, these recommendations can help prepare the respective dossiers and documentation.

2.5. Intended audience

These recommendations are intended for all researchers working with visual data who are interested in making their data “open”. While we emphasize visual social research, many sections will be relevant across disciplines and are designed to support both experienced scholars and those at earlier stages of their academic careers, such as students and post-docs. We recognize that an increasing number of researchers are engaging with visual materials, as visuals have become ubiquitous elements in today’s media and communication environments. For this reason, we hope that even experienced researchers who may not have previously worked with visual data might find these recommendations useful as they expand their methodological toolkit.

3. Visual data & open science

Key take-aways

- Visual social research is an interdisciplinary field that studies and (co)creates diverse visual materials, such as photographs, videos, memes, or conceptual diagrams, as both data and analytical tools to explore social and cultural phenomena. These visuals may be found, participant-created, or researcher-produced, and serve in both the analysis *of* visuals and research *with* visuals.
- Because visual data are highly context-dependent and culturally embedded, open data practices in visual research must account for ethical, interpretive, and methodological complexity. This includes careful preparation, contextualization, and reflection on the meaning and use of such data within diverse research traditions.
- To allow open science, open visual research should enable access and reuse of visuals. Furthermore it should apply FAIR principles, that requires persistent identifiers and metadata (findable), suitable repositories and access conditions (accessible), non-proprietary formats for integration (interoperable), and clear licensing for reuse (reusable).
- Beyond legal compliance, researchers must uphold ethical responsibility, including informed consent, cultural sensitivity, and the minimization of harm, especially when working with sensitive or vulnerable communities.

3.1. What are visual data?

These guidelines were developed for the context of *visual social research*. Understood very broadly, visual social research is a highly heterogeneous and interdisciplinary field that utilizes visual materials, such as photographs, films, drawings, and digital media, as both sources of data and tools for analysis in studying social and cultural phenomena. Moreover, it uses visual methods to explore social phenomena. The guidelines recognize that visual communication plays a crucial role in shaping human interactions, identities, and socio-cultural structures.

This approach not only involves the analysis of existing visual representations and materials but also the (co)creation of visual data to explore lived experiences and cultural meanings. Situated in this tradition, visual data can be very heterogeneous forms of visual representations that can serve as research data. For example, Pauwels (2020) distinguishes between found visuals, such as photographs, advertisements, and online media, which were not originally intended for research, and researcher-instigated visuals, including images created by researchers, participant-created images, video recordings, and conceptual diagrams. Moreover, visuals are used or (co)created when visual methods are applied. In other words, it includes research *of* visuals as well as research *with* visuals (Lobinger, 2016). In the discussion within the three workshops, for example, the following kinds of “visual data” were mentioned: personal images, social media images, journalistic images, war and atrocity images, Covid-19 memes, far-right extremists' visual messages, sensitive images, non-verbal facial expressions, and many more.

This very brief presentation of what visual data is will be challenged in chapter 2 of this document. As we will see, visuals are highly context-dependent and require careful interpretation within their cultural and social contexts and practices, which has implications for

open data practices and how visual data need to be prepared. Moreover, visual social research spans heterogeneous theoretical and methodological paradigms, consequently yielding diverse challenges for open data practices.

3.2. Open data & open science

The Open Knowledge Foundation, a global, non-profit network, defines *open* knowledge as “knowledge, promoting a robust common in which anyone may participate, and interoperability is maximized” (Open Knowledge Foundation, n.d.a). The broadest approach is provided by the umbrella term “open science,” which “describes the various efforts and activities which aim to reach this goal of bringing science to all” (Swiss Academies of Arts and Sciences, n.d.). Open science, thus, summarized very briefly, promotes the interconnectedness and democratization of knowledge and creates added value for society (swissuniversities, n.d.).

Free access to scientific publications and research data, including visual research data, is thus an essential component of open science, which aims to constantly improve the quality of scientific work. Open visual research data is a dimension of open science, facilitating access to and reuse of visual research data (where appropriate). Through the principles of open access and reusability of research data, open research data (ORD) practices support transparent and reproducible research findings. The idea of ORD also promotes collaboration by making it easier for researchers to share their knowledge across disciplines, legal systems, and borders, enabling creativity and innovation (swissuniversities, n.d.). Similarly, the Open Data Handbook of the Open Knowledge Foundation considers open data as “data that can be freely used, re-used and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and share alike.” (Open Knowledge Foundation, n.d.b.). Open science is typically expected to respect the findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) principles.

3.3. FAIR principles

Obstacles to data discovery and reuse pose significant challenges for both researchers and computational systems, ultimately increasing the time and effort required for scientific inquiry. These difficulties often stem from insufficient consideration of how digital resources are created, curated, and preserved. In response to these issues, the FAIR Guiding Principles were created, which aim to make research data *Findable*, *Accessible*, *Interoperable*, and *Reusable*. For more information, see Martone (2015) and Wilkinson et al. (2016).

In the following, the four FAIR principles (GO FAIR, n.d.) are briefly explained with a focus on visual research data:

- *Findable*: Visual research data should be easy to find for both humans and computers. This means they should always be accompanied by metadata and descriptions that provide context for the visuals. Additionally, a unique and persistent identifier, such as a DOI (Digital Object Identifier), should be assigned.
- *Accessible*: Visual research data should be accessible online, deposited in a trusted data repository suitable for visuals, and have clear access conditions (restricted or open access).
- *Interoperable*: Visual research data should be shared in a format that facilitates integrations with other data and ensures interoperability with applications or workflows for analysis, storage, and processing. Visuals should be published in a format that is easily accessible and does not require restrictive or proprietary software.
- *Reusable*: Visual research data should be shared under a clear license that specifies the conditions for their reuse. This can be a Creative Commons license, or a license specifically created for that occasion.

3.4. Ethical practices and legal standards

When dealing with open visual data, both legal, ethical, and pragmatic considerations must be addressed. Legally, issues such as copyright, licensing, personality rights, and data protection laws, e.g., regarding identifiable individuals, must be followed to avoid violations. However, ethically, researchers must often go beyond legal compliance to ensure a responsible and respectful use of visuals, considering factors like informed consent, cultural sensitivity, potential misuse, and potential impacts on vulnerable communities.

In these recommendations, we aim to address legal, ethical, and pragmatic aspects, while highlighting the diverse sensitivities that may arise when working with visual research data. In the following part, we will discuss these aspects with respect to the peculiarities of visual social research, point to challenges, benefits, and risks, and give, where possible, recommendations or questions that help researchers make informed decisions.

4. Considerations when sharing visual data (openly)

Key take-aways

- Visuals are sensitive, context-rich, and often hard to anonymize meaning that they can expose participants through identifiable details, metadata, or reverse-image searches. Risks also include amplification, misuse, and retraumatization.
- Openness cannot be assumed as a default. The appropriate level depends on the research paradigm, aims, data type, populations involved, and the potential value of sharing.
- Researchers must think about ethical and legal aspects regarding visual open data practices at the start of the research project. Tackling these aspects just before publishing your data is too late.

Ethical considerations:

- *Consent as an ongoing process*: Consent should be informed, clear, accessible, and ideally modular. It should also be revisited at key research stages. It protects participants, not just institutions, and researchers must prepare for scenarios where it is later revoked.
- *Anonymization*: Traditional techniques such as blurring or pixelation often reduce meaning and may undermine participants' agency. Alternatives include reenactment, illustration, AI replicas, or ethical fabrication. All the decisions taken should be contextual and ideally involve participants.
- *Textual substitution*: Replacing visuals with descriptions may reduce risks but is time-consuming, reductive, and methodologically limited. Automated captioning adds risks of bias and inaccuracy. Textual substitution can be useful as a partial solution but not as a full replacement.

Legal considerations:

- *Data protection and confidentiality*: Visuals containing personal data require consent. Risks of indirect identification (through context or metadata) must be considered.
- *Copyright and ownership*: Only share visuals when rights are clear. Check originality, ownership, and the legal framework of the country where sharing occurs.
- *Licensing*: Use Creative Commons licenses (CC0, CC BY, CC BY-SA) only for fully open access. For restricted access, tailored or project-specific licenses may be more appropriate. Remember that licenses do not override data protection law.

In this section, we will explore key considerations related to visual open data practices. First, we will discuss the importance of open visual data. Subsequently, we examine ethical issues through the lens of various theoretical and empirical research paradigms. Then, we will turn to the legal considerations involved.

4.1. The need for open visual data and its challenges

As argued above, aligning visual research with the aim of open science, when done adequately, brings important benefits in terms of enhanced transparency, replicability, accessibility, and aims to improve research rigor and democratize knowledge production, collaboration, and research efficiency.

Visuals play diverse and highly important roles throughout the research process. For example, visuals can be the examined research material itself in qualitative or quantitative visual (content) analyses, stimuli in experiments, visual tools used for elicitation, elements of participatory research, observational material, supports in data interpretation through models, visualizations or networks, and many more. Despite their epistemic relevance, visuals are rarely made visible in research outputs, are often not available in peer-review processes, and are thus not discussed in-depth in methodological or theoretical terms, leading to gaps in transparency, reproducibility, and interpretative depth. Overall, the focus on visuals in academic publications has been somewhat limited (Lobinger et al., 2019)² as, traditionally, scholarly outputs are still heavily text-centered and typically just allow for a few images to be included, reflecting a long history of logocentrism. Notable exceptions are of course academic journals in the field of visual research that allow for visual formats, such as visual essays. For some studies, showing and sharing the visuals that are used in research can be essential. For example, verbal interpretations in visual analyses are difficult to evaluate without knowing the visuals they refer to. Whether stimuli that are used in experiments represent a successful operationalization of the concepts under investigation cannot be assessed without investigating the visual material and the description of operationalization (Krämer, 2015). These two examples highlight the relevance of providing open visual data. We argue that promoting visual transparency, openness, and reflexivity in both research and publication should generally be the aim, as it can enhance the validity and impact of visual scholarship.

However, visual open data practices also raise complex ethical, legal, pragmatic, and contextual challenges that require careful attention. While the open science movement focuses mostly on the advantages of data sharing, the potential risks, particularly those affecting research participants, also need to be foregrounded. Whether open science practices are employed, the imperative that research must avoid harm to participants remains the core concern.

Furthermore, an important question regards whether prevailing open data expectations really support qualitative rigor. In this regard, Prosser et al. (2023) note potential ethical concerns and disadvantages for qualitative researchers in peer review and publication contexts compared to quantitative approaches. Others have highlighted the potential risk of marginalization of research areas and research on vulnerable groups and communities (Fox et al., 2021). These considerations show that visual open data practices are not simply about making research data available as a last step of the research project. They are connected to detailed reflections that are related to, e.g., the research discipline and paradigm, epistemological stance, type of data collected or used, research aim, researched populations, and usefulness for open data. These aspects will be focused on in the sections below. We thus second the plea by Prosser et al. (2023, p. 1635) that open data guidelines should “move away from a universal ‘one-size-fits-all’ approach”.

² This section summarizes a previous discussion presented in Lobinger et al. (2019).

4.2. Implications of research traditions and epistemological perspectives

In the previous paragraph, we have highlighted the relevance of sharing visuals in open data practices. However, depending on the research approach, not only the visual data that have been collected and/or analyzed might be the relevant data to be shared. Instead, it may also be necessary to make available *contextual information*, analytical approaches, and reflexive accounts to support meaningful and responsible reuse of open data, particularly in ways that go beyond the narrow focus on “replicability,” which remains a central concern, primarily within quantitative research paradigms.

In some approaches of visual social research, and most importantly in participatory approaches and qualitative interpretative approaches, questions of reflexivity and researcher positionality are central to the production or collection, selection, editing, handling, and interpretation of data. In this case, it becomes essential to document the researcher's role, power differentials, biases, positionality, context, and engagement, which makes these *reflexive accounts* an essential part of the data itself. Prosser et al. (2023) thus ask: “But if reflexive accounts are crucial to understanding research data or even to be research data, what are the implications for opening such data?” and “And what are the implications of other researchers accessing and using different kinds of open qualitative data?”. These concerns prompt broader reflection on what kinds of data should be shared, for which purposes, how useful this actually is, and how openness intersects with the rigor and integrity of qualitative inquiry. Branney et al. (2019) recommend a context-consent meta-framework for secondary qualitative research using open data, especially on sensitive topics. This involves assessing the original study's ethical, methodological, and contextual suitability for new research aims. When visual data are involved, such reflection is crucial due to risks of, e.g., identifiability and contextual sensitivity. As Prosser et al. (2023) highlight, providing clear documentation of the original research context and ethics enhances the rigour and ethical grounding of secondary analysis involving open visual data.

For example, approaches of visual ethnography or action research are based on a trust-building approach between researchers and the individuals and communities who participate (Pauwels, 2015; Peattie, 2025). Trust is not a fixed starting condition for conducting research but is an evolving, negotiated element of the research relationship (Pink, 2013). Often, very dense material is collected, for example, interviews with personal and intimate narrations that go beyond the research aim or are not directly related to it. “These participants' accounts are produced within a particular context, and it is the researcher's ethical responsibility to represent participants' accounts in ways that reflect these *contextual specificities within which it was produced*, and in keeping with the ways participants intended for them to be represented and used” (Prosser et al., 2023). This would mean that when sharing visuals, it must be ensured that the shared visual data will not be used for different purposes or to investigate other phenomena than those discussed with the participants for informed consent (see below). While providing data together with “*guidelines for future data use*” might be a good starting point, it remains unclear how the actual intended reuse can be guaranteed and monitored in fully open data practices. In fact, Prosser et al. (2023) provide a nuanced discussion, emphasizing that there cannot be an automatic imperative to make data publicly available. Instead, they emphasize the ethical responsibility to discern when withholding data is the more appropriate and respectful course of action, adding that for some researchers “the idea of sharing data with anyone other than participants is anathema to their professional values and is seen as compromising the future of such research” (Prosser et al., 2023, p. 1648).

Quantitative visual research presents distinct challenges in the context of open science and data transparency. While discussions around the so-called “replicability crisis” have prompted calls for greater openness in data sharing across the social sciences (Ioannidis, 2005), visual data pose particular challenges. In large-scale content analyses, e.g., when examining representation patterns in visual journalism, researchers often work with extensive image datasets that they do not own or cannot legally redistribute or publish without making a fair use or fair dealing argument that not all publishers will accept. Copyright restrictions, platform terms of service, and the ethical use of third-party images limit the feasibility of open data

practices. Moreover, duplicating existing archives may be redundant or infeasible due to legal constraints. These issues are especially pronounced in studies that analyze images drawn from social media platforms. In such cases, even when technically accessible, visual data may contain personal or sensitive content that raises significant privacy concerns. The Association of Internet Researchers (AoIR) provides ethical guidelines for such scenarios, emphasizing informed consent, contextual integrity, and minimizing harm (Markham & Buchanan, 2012). Thus, while reproducibility is a legitimate and important goal, the nature of visual data and legal contexts often requires a more nuanced approach that balances openness with ethical and legal responsibility (Clark, 2020).

We argue that, from an *ethical point of view*, open data poses particular challenges in the field of visual social research, where concerns around privacy, informed consent, the role of context and possible misrepresentation are highly pronounced and demand thoughtful, responsible approaches, particularly, but not only, because visual data contain very dense visual cues and are often difficult to anonymize. As we will argue further below, the use of open visual data raises concerns about consent, especially when the images involve vulnerable or marginalized groups or individuals who may not fully understand the implications of their data being shared openly. Also, cultural sensitivities must be considered, as some images may have significant meaning within the communities in which they are used, and their open distribution could lead to exploitation or harm. Additionally, the potential for misuse or misinterpretation of visual data is high, as images can be easily altered or taken out of context. And context, as has been argued above, is particularly important for making sense of visual data.

From a *legal point of view*, issues such as copyright, intellectual property rights, and data protection laws can complicate the sharing and reuse of visual data. Images can contain copyrighted material or include identifiable individuals, which can raise privacy concerns. Without clear and appropriate licenses, researchers might thus inadvertently violate legal restrictions.

Also, regarding *technical issues*, some challenges emerge: Visual research data often come in large file sizes and diverse formats, making them difficult to edit, store, manage, and share using existing repositories and infrastructure, particularly as most repositories were developed for storing numeric or language data. Moreover, the lack of standardized metadata and issues regarding interoperability make it difficult to prepare data for sharing and discovery, and the use of visual data across different platforms.

4.3. Ethical considerations

4.3.1. Minimizing harm

The principle of *minimizing harm* in research is a cornerstone of ethical inquiry, emphasizing the responsibility of researchers to avoid or reduce potential physical, psychological, social, or reputational risks to participants. In visual social research, where images, video, or visual representations of individuals and communities are involved, this principle takes on added importance (Lobinger et al., 2019) regarding various aspects, such as informed consent, informational self-determination, and risk mitigation. This regards data collection and analysis, as well as the publication, storage, and sharing of research findings and data (Pauwels, 2008, 2015; Waycott et al., 2015; Wiles et al., 2011). For example, visual data can inadvertently expose identities, cultural contexts, or sensitive circumstances, even when anonymization is attempted. Therefore, researchers must carefully consider consent, context, and dissemination to ensure that the dignity, safety, and privacy of research participants are preserved, particularly when working with vulnerable or marginalized populations. Late et al. (2024) discuss several challenges and ethical considerations of sharing image data based on expert interviews. Their findings highlight concerns like privacy, consent, and data protection, especially when dealing with sensitive or identifiable images.

Anonymization plays a crucial role in minimizing harm by reducing the risk that research participants and other related individuals can be identified from visual data, especially in cases where images contain recognizable features, locations, or contextual cues that could compromise participant privacy. However, Allen (2015) critically argues that anonymization

should not be a “normalized” or “self-evident” principle imposed by ethics committees. In fact, while anonymization might be a key principle of many research approaches, it is not a default decision (Allen, 2015). Particularly, in approaches such as “photovoice” and similar participatory methodologies, it is imperative to give a “visual voice” to participants. Even within research traditions that prioritize anonymizing visual data, the methods used to achieve anonymity are often complex and difficult to implement effectively (see the section on Anonymization below).

Minimizing harm, with respect to visuals, also means evaluating the “*object*” image, and not the visual representational level alone. In fact, a major consideration is the hidden risks embedded in image metadata, such as geographical coordinates, timestamps, and device information. As Ghazinour and Ponchak (2017) demonstrate for social media images, metadata can make it possible to track or identify individuals even when images appear anonymized, particularly when shared on open platforms. This complicates informed consent, as participants may not fully understand the digital traceability of their images. The same goes for reverse image search. Thereby, the traceability of visual data on social media, including through reverse image search and computer vision, not only raises the risk of identification, but also the risk of misidentification. Misidentification occurs when individuals or contexts are wrongly identified based on visual data. This could happen due to contextual cues such as location, clothing, or timing, even if efforts have been made to anonymize the material.

Another risk that might occur does not regard research participants themselves. Rather, it poses a societal risk due to *amplification* or *transformation*. Amplification in visual social research refers to the unintended spread and escalation or appropriation of visual content beyond its original context, which can raise significant ethical concerns. When images, especially those depicting sensitive, political, or controversial subjects, are shared or republished, they may be co-opted by third parties, distorted, or used to reinforce harmful narratives. This can result in the magnification of extremist views, the exploitation of participants' representations, or the perpetuation of stereotypes (see also Phillips, 2015). The ethical problem lies in the researcher's limited control over how visual material circulates once it enters public or digital spaces, which can expose individuals or communities to unforeseen risks. Amplification or transformation also risks overshadowing the intended message of the research, turning ethically produced content into tools for misinformation, sensationalism, or ideological agendas. Therefore, researchers must consider not only how images are created and shared but also how they might be interpreted and repurposed in wider contexts.

Researchers must also weigh *political and legal shifts* that could render harmless data harmful after publication. As Prosser et al. (2023) warn, changes in political decisions and law might make data that once seemed neutral become incriminating or dangerous for participants.

Moreover, visual research, especially researching *war and conflict* or *trauma-related contexts*, carries heightened risk. Traumatization or re-traumatization, whether of participants, researchers, or audiences, is a real concern. Researchers examining graphic content (e.g., war imagery or scenes of death) must consider not only whether showing such images is necessary but also how they are presented. This also implies ethical reflections on whether and how larger data collections of potentially (re)traumatizing images should be placed in research repositories.

Many more challenges exist regarding the obligation to minimize harm. Research must be sensitive to its subject matter and anticipate potential risks in advance. Tools and guidance that support researchers in making adequate decisions include responsive consent processes (see below), trauma-informed protocols, detailed ethical evaluations, continuous risk assessment, and culturally aware decision-making, particularly when working with vulnerable groups or publishing on contested topics. As visual social research continues to grow, so too must our ethical frameworks evolve to protect those rendered visible in our work. This applies equally to the open sharing of visual research data.

4.3.2. Consent

Ethical visual research depends on building and maintaining transparent, respectful relationships that support collaborative image-making and participant empowerment (Banks, 2001; Harper, 1998). In general, the process of obtaining and maintaining consent aims to enable participants to make informed decisions about their research participation and to *protect them from harm*, thus considering potential uses of visual material and possible emotional, reputational, or cultural impacts (Pink, 2013; Gross et al., 1988). Ethical guidelines across diverse fields (see e.g., Humphreys et al., 2019; Pink, 2013; Wiles et al., 2008), highlight that, ideally, consent should be *informed, voluntary, modular*, and understood as a *dynamic process*. With respect to obtaining consent for visual open data practices, there are no existing guidelines, which is why in the following, we build upon recommendations and good practices that have already been established for publishing images in research publications.

In this regard, we emphasize that, most importantly, consent should not be seen as a merely “contractual” approach (Pauwels, 2008) that protects researchers, universities, or publishers. Instead, the *focus should be put on research participants*. This means that researchers should seek to obtain truly informed, voluntary, and ongoing consent, which requires that the participant should be *fully aware of the implications of open data practices*. As Pauwels (2008) argues, truly informed consent is an ideal principle that might be impossible to achieve in practice. With respect to open data this means that participants should be fully aware of the implications of open visual open data practices and future uses, which even for researchers that are familiar with the system of academic publication and documentation is sometimes difficult to assess. Hence, following the suggestions by Fox et al. (2021) “researchers should employ thorough, clear, and accessible informed consent.” This means that the explanation to participants should be easily understandable, should explain how participants’ data will be treated, how it will be made available, who will be able to see and (re)use it, and what risks this might entail.

As these considerations show, the challenging task of obtaining truly informed consent needs to be planned accordingly. This means that adequate time for informing participants needs to be allocated. How consent will be obtained and what implications this has for the later use of visuals in e.g., analysis, publication, and open data practices, already needs to be considered at the *very start of the project*, typically when the data management plan (see below) is set up.

Modular consent is a useful way for providing participants with choices instead of making all-or-nothing decisions (Prieto-Blanco, 2021; Fox et al., 2021; Wiles et al. 2008). This means that, instead of asking for a one-time, general consent for all procedures and data uses, modular consent allows individuals to agree to certain elements of participation (e.g., being interviewed) while declining others (e.g., image publication). This allows for more granular control and ethical clarity. When it comes to visuals and open data practices, it is advisable to *discuss consent for every single visual item* provided, as some visuals might be considered more sensitive by participants than others. This means that modular consent should ideally be obtained for every visual item and allow for gradual decisions regarding the use of the respective element (Branney et al., 2019), how it needs to be anonymized (if applicable, see the section on anonymization below), and options of data sharing.

As always, this does not apply to all research projects; rather *context sensitive* decisions need to be foregrounded. For example, in some research contexts, it might be advisable to revisit consent at key stages, which could be before public dissemination, publication (Pink, 2013; Humphreys et al., 2019), or before uploading them to a repository. In any case, researchers should consider *consent as a process* rather than as a static one-time event (Prosser, 2000). As Fox et al. (2021) point out, participants may wish to *withdraw or modify* their consent to open data sharing when they learn more about the research project, its character, and objectives. While taking part, they might in fact develop a better understanding or “feeling” of the research aim and process. Ultimately, however, this also yields problems. For example, what should be done when data are already made available, and participants later revoke their consent?

A further important assessment regards *whether participants are capable of giving full consent* or whether other people need to be involved. For example, as Pink (2013) argues, in certain communities, image use might be governed by communal norms rather than individual autonomy, which necessitates *communal consent*. Moreover, when it comes to visual data, other people than the participants might be the owners of the images or be represented within them. This is typically reflected in detail in legal decisions, but should also be an integral element of the ethical decisions in the context of consent.

Most importantly, as protecting participants from harm is the most important guiding principle, having obtained consent from the participants for visual open data practices *does not automatically mean visual data should be made available*. It is the responsibility of the researchers to additionally reflect on implications and not directly foreseen uses, assess the risks before proceeding with data sharing, and selecting the degrees of openness that are deemed suitable and the ways in which visual data need to be prepared (see e.g., the section on anonymization below).

Finally, when sharing visual data in an adequately selected manner, the conditions of consent should also be *made transparent for future researchers* intending to (re)use the data (Branney et al. 2019). This is a key step to ensure participants' decisions are honored in future research.

Important questions in this regard are:

- How can researchers make sure that participants understand the implications of visual open data practices?
- Can consent be obtained from the research participants or do further people need to be considered/contacted?
- How can the necessary information for informed consent with respect to visual open data practices be presented in an accessible, understandable way? (see consent form below). How granular should modular consent be without becoming overly complex (e.g., how many decisions per visual element/package of visual elements are appropriate)?
- Which degrees of openness are consented to by the participants? How can consent be obtained technically? (see section on consent forms below).
- How do visual data need to be prepared (e.g., cleaned, edited, transformed, or anonymized)?
- How can missing elements of the dataset for which consent was not obtained be made transparent?
- What should be done if consent is revoked after the data have already been published in an open data repository?
- How can the conditions of consent be available to future researchers (re)using the data?

4.3.3. Anonymization of visual data

Ethical considerations typically necessitate the anonymization or pseudonymization of data. However, images are very rich elements that contain many different visual cues. For example, images often show rich contextual details, making it harder to fully anonymize individuals and their environments. A key challenge with respect to anonymizing is finding ways to protect the anonymity of depicted individuals and of research participants in general, *without compromising crucial research insights*. Extensive blurring, cropping, or pixelating might even make images useless when shared in open data practices. As this is a core element of decisions underlying visual open data practices, in the following, we highlight some of the main techniques that have been suggested in the context of visual social research.

Traditional ways of anonymizing images include *pixelation, facial blurring techniques, cropping*, or using *black-out-bars (black masking)*. While these are techniques that are commonly suggested by ethical boards, researchers in visual research have pointed out a series of problems related to these approaches. Some issues concern the agency and identity

of the participants. For example, black bars have been associated with criminality and dehumanization (Venema et al., 2020; Wiles et al., 2011), while cropping images to portions that do not show faces might objectify the respective individuals due to a focus on their body or body parts (Allen, 2015). These techniques would then, in fact, go against visual ethics. And, to guarantee anonymity, often many aspects of an image need to be blurred or pixelated (e.g., backgrounds, buildings, and/or other people). Consequently, some issues related to these techniques regard the usefulness of images in publication and open data practices. For example, Allen (2015, p. 295) has argued that these practices “mask content into obscurity”, making them essentially useless for meaning making. She even calls the consequences “a mockery of the value of visual data and the voice of participants”. Allen (2015) particularly underscores that anonymization is not always in line with the research paradigm (see section 4.2.).

Another approach to protecting the anonymity of participants is to *recreate* or *transform* images when presenting research findings. Visual researchers have used *reenactment with actors* instead of the participants for recreating images that were central to showing research findings, which allows for maintaining the essence and meaning of the scene (e.g., also showing relevant facial expressions) while guaranteeing anonymity to original participants. This has been done for both still images (Reißmann, 2012) and film material (Cook & Hubbard, 2007). Certainly, this is an approach that requires extensive resources and might be feasible for a few selected visuals used in publications, but not for open data practices in which all the collected material should ideally be shared. Moreover, from an ethical point of view, it needs to be ensured that the recreated elements are in line with the original ideal of the participants. This also applies to recent approaches in which recreation was not performed with actors recreating scenes but with the help of manual illustration or AI replicas for publications or public dissemination (Kamelski & Olivos, 2025; Lobinger, 2025).

Finally, *fabrication* (Markham, 2012) or *visual ethical fabrication* (Tiidenberg, 2014, 2018; Warfield et al., 2019) have been proposed. These are alternation techniques that work on the visual level of the image. Also here, the aim is to modify images through editing tools to obscure identity while maintaining meaning (Markham, 2012; Tiidenberg, 2018). Techniques include altering colors, styles, or compositions to prevent reverse image identification (Warfield et al., 2019). The aim is generally twofold: to *hinder recognition*, but also to reduce the risk of finding the image with the help of search engines. This is an important aspect as images are often posted online and might be retrievable due to the searchability of the web and the increasing progress of machine vision techniques.

Despite these methods, no universal solution exists for anonymizing visual data in publications or in research repositories. Decisions must be made contextually and in collaboration with research participants. The challenge, as Warfield et al. (2019) describe it, lies in the “protection-patronizing dilemma” that is in the question of how to safeguard identities without diminishing individuals’ agency in research representation.

4.3.4. Substituting visual data with textual descriptions

Substituting visual data with textual descriptions might at first be seen as a pragmatic response to concerns surrounding data protection, copyright, and research ethics when engaging in visual open data practices. Particularly under data protection frameworks such as the European Union’s General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2016/679, 2016), researchers are increasingly expected to minimize the use of personally identifiable information. Translating images into verbal descriptions could then hypothetically serve as an effective means of abstraction, allowing researchers to retain the essential analytical content of a visual while omitting “unnecessary” or sensitive personal detail. For example, instead of including a photo that reveals the identity of a subject, researchers might describe the scene in general, anonymized terms, thereby safeguarding the individual’s privacy while maintaining the integrity of the analysis.

However, beyond legal considerations, the use of textual descriptions raises significant methodological and epistemological challenges. Creating precise and context-sensitive descriptions of visual material is labor-intensive and becomes increasingly impractical with

larger datasets. Short descriptions, on the other hand, tend to lack analytical value. Furthermore, the act of description itself is inherently reductive and is always based on selection and the omission of a variety of dense information. Generally, the visual modality possesses affordances that cannot be fully transposed into linguistic form. Visual elements such as color, spatial arrangement, aspect ratio, the relationship between positive and negative space, texture, gesture, and affect resist clean translation into text, a limitation long acknowledged in multimodal theory (e.g., Kress & van Leeuwen, 2006). Thus, descriptions not only risk omitting subtleties of the visual but may also distort their meaning by framing them through interpretive filters embedded in language. This gap between modes is further complicated by the question of automation. While automatic image captioning technologies promise efficiency, they also raise critical concerns around accuracy, privacy, and ethical governance. Automated tools may introduce biases, reproduce stereotypes, or mistakenly include personally identifiable features, all of which could undermine data protection efforts.

There is thus an unresolved tension in the very notion of an "image description" that again needs to be reflected with respect to the research project.

- What constitutes a sufficient description?
- How much detail is too much, in that it allows for indirect identification?
- Which function does the description of visual data assume? Does it serve to understand a verbal transcript in which visual data was mentioned or should it allow for a re-analysis of the visual data, which is hardly achievable?

These ambiguities demand methodological reflexivity and, in some contexts, may require researchers to weigh image description as an intermediate or "partial openness" strategy that navigates between full data disclosure and complete redaction. In any case, researchers must approach image descriptions not merely as neutral substitutes but as active representations with their own stakes, limitations, and responsibilities.

Permission to publish textual representations derived from visual data also needs to be obtained in the process of informed consent (see above). Participants may perceive descriptions as less invasive, but they may still reveal sensitive contextual information or serve as proxies for the original image, thereby reintroducing ethical risks. Lastly, a widespread misconception is that the act of describing an image circumvents copyright restrictions. Rather, textual descriptions of copyrighted visual works may themselves be considered a use of the work (Barrelet et al., 2021) under most copyright regimes. Whether the image is reproduced directly or through a paraphrased representation in another modality, such as text, the transformation still typically requires permission from the original rights holder. This principle underscores that the mode of reproduction, be it visual or verbal, does not fundamentally alter the legal boundaries around creative ownership in some contexts.

4.4. Legal considerations

The dissemination of research data necessitates careful consideration of relevant legal frameworks, particularly in relation to intellectual property rights and the protection of personal data. These legal dimensions become especially intricate in the context of visual research data, which often raise unique challenges due to their identifiable and context-rich nature.

As open research data increasingly transcend national borders, researchers are required to navigate a multiplicity of legal systems. This transnational dimension underscores the importance of assessing each case individually to ascertain the applicable national or regional legislation.

In these Recommendations, we draw upon the principal international legal norms pertaining to copyright and data protection in order to provide a foundational framework for addressing these issues in the context of visual research data.

4.4.1. Confidentiality / Data protection / Privacy

In this section, the most relevant concepts regarding data protection and privacy will be explained to help researchers understand whether they are allowed to share a visual *from a purely data protection point of view*.

The general rule is that visuals containing elements that might identify a person (personal data) can only be shared with the consent of the person. Figure 1 guides the researcher through the most relevant data protection questions. Below, each question is briefly explained along with its related legal concepts, providing researchers with the necessary guidance to make informed decisions.

Figure 1 - Data protection questions to address when publishing visual research data

Question 1: Are there elements that could identify a person?

Personal data includes all elements that allow identifying a person in an unambiguous way. Data protection laws define personal data as any information that relates to an identified or identifiable individual. This includes not only data that directly reveals a person's identity, such as visuals where individuals are clearly recognizable, but also information that, when combined with other data, could lead to identification. For example, a photograph of a pink car parked in front of a restaurant in a small town may be considered personal data, even if no person is visible, because residents might easily associate the car with its owner. This also includes hidden metadata linked to a visual like "geotags for locations, as well as camera identification numbers and time stamps." (Ghazinour & Ponchak, 2017).

In this regard, *internal confidentiality* also needs to be considered and might pose challenges (Tolich, 2004). Internal confidentiality typically becomes a critical issue in qualitative or ethnographic visual social research, especially when working with small or marginalized communities or with individuals who are closely related to each other. Individuals who are connected to one another may easily recognize people in visuals based on details such as jewelry, clothing, tattoos, hair, gestures, or gait, even when efforts have been made to anonymize them. Finally, ensuring confidentiality becomes especially challenging when images are taken by participants themselves as part of a research project. Participants may use the images they create in ways that do not align with the project's ethical goals. Moreover, individuals might upload photos or videos produced for research purposes to social media platforms or other websites.

Personal data may also be classified as *sensitive*, depending on its content. Information concerning an individual's health, religious or political beliefs, sexual orientation, or gender identity, or involvement in criminal proceedings is regarded as sensitive. Visuals depicting identifiable people are very likely to fall under this category as they can easily reveal sensitive details. For example, a person wearing glasses might indicate a health condition, or a person

wearing a headscarf or a chain with a cross pendant might indicate a religious affiliation. In this case, it is even more important to protect the privacy of the people involved.

When sharing sensitive data, explicit consent is required. When sharing personal non-sensitive data, implicit consent might be sufficient. However, before explicit or implicit consent, the person involved must be clearly informed about how their personal data would be used. Researchers should consult the data protection law that applies to their specific case and geographical context to be sure regarding the required form of consent.

If the visuals do not contain personal data, data protection laws do not apply, and the visuals can be shared openly from a purely data protection point of view. When visuals contain personal data (sensitive or non-sensitive), researchers must implement appropriate confidentiality and security measures to safeguard individuals' privacy, for example, through anonymization techniques (see section 4.3.3.).

Generally, *data protection laws only apply to living people* (people alive). However, there might be national or regional differences. With regard to visuals, this means that if a person was alive at the time a picture or video is taken for research purposes, data protection laws apply to the collection and use of their personal data during their lifetime, but generally no longer after their death. However, researchers still need to consider the privacy of their relatives and other living individuals that might be connected to the data. In principle, researchers do not need permission under data protection law to share visuals of individuals who are already deceased at the time of sharing.

It is further important to distinguish between a *public figure's private life and public life*. In general, visuals of public figures related to their public activities can be shared without consent. However, sharing images that reveal private information about public figures is a sensitive and often controversial matter, with legal regulations varying from country to country. Therefore, if visuals concern public figures' private lives, researchers need to consult the relevant laws to determine whether consent is required and in what form.

Some regional data protection laws extend their protection not only to personal data of individuals but also to *company data*. In this case, the same principles that apply to the processing of personal data, such as consent, transparency, and risk assessment, may also apply to data concerning companies. Researchers must consult the relevant data protection laws to determine whether such protections apply when sharing visual research data. If they do not apply, researchers are generally not required to seek the company's permission to release the data, unless a non-disclosure agreement is in place. This might be particularly relevant to metadata accompanying visuals.

Question 2: Can visuals be fully anonymized?

Anonymization is not always feasible or desirable (see section 4.3.3.). In some cases, anonymization might significantly alter the visuals to the point of compromising their research value. In other cases, participants may wish to remain identifiable because they find the research as empowering. In such situations, obtaining proper informed consent is essential for the lawful sharing of research visual research data.

If the visual has been fully anonymized, it can be freely shared from a purely data protection point of view. In all other cases, consent of the identifiable people in the visual needs to be collected. For more details on anonymization and the respective ethical considerations, see section 4.3.3.

Question 3: Has consent been obtained for sharing the visuals?

Generally, consent is required under the more stringent data protection laws (e.g., the GDPR). However, consent requirements vary by national or regional legislation (e.g., whether implicit consent is sufficient or explicit consent is mandatory, or whether additional conditions apply when personal data is transferred or even just visible from abroad, such as when uploading visuals to an open access repository). Researchers should check the applicable data

protection laws to determine the appropriate form of consent needed for sharing their visual research data.

The person granting consent must be able to understand the consequences of sharing their personal data. If this is not the case, because of mental issues or because the person involved is underaged, the person legally responsible (parents or guardian) of the person involved may grant consent on behalf of their wishes. Researchers must consult the appropriate legislation to determine at which age parents must grant consent on behalf of their children. From an ethical point of view, consent is interpreted in a stricter way and should always be requested when sharing visuals. Ethics strongly focuses on the protection of participants and making them fully aware of the implications of open data practices and future uses. More on this can be found in section 2.2.

4.4.2. Copyright: Authorship & Ownership

In this section, the most relevant concepts regarding copyright will be explained to help researchers understand *whether they are allowed to share a visual from a purely copyright protection point of view*.

The general rule is that in order to share copyright-protected visuals, researchers need the permission of the rights holder.

The following decision tree (see Figure 2) guides the researcher through the most relevant copyright questions. Below, each question is briefly explained along with its related legal concepts, providing researchers with the necessary guidance to make informed decisions.

Figure 2 - Copyright questions to address when publishing visual research data

Question 1: Which national laws apply?

Even though the core principles of copyright are similar across different national legislations, there are national differences, especially regarding the duration of protection, the treatment of some forms (e.g., photographs), and the conditions of copyright exceptions.

It is therefore fundamental that researchers, in a first step, understand which national legislation(s) apply when sharing the visuals in question.

The *Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works* (Berne Convention, 1979) was established in 1886 and signed by 181 countries as of 2025. It is an international treaty that provides some minimal protection to be granted and shared standards among the signatory countries. It is a framework that harmonizes national copyright laws, aiming to safeguard the rights of authors over their creations. It ensures that authors automatically hold copyright over their works, such as books, music, films, videos, photographs, and paintings, without the need for formal registration. The Convention has binding effects on signatory countries, which are required to incorporate its principles into their national copyright legislation.

The Convention introduces the “*territoriality principle*,” which determines the applicable copyright law when multiple countries are involved. According to this principle, set by art. 5 of the Convention, the copyright law of the country where the protected work is used applies. For example, if a video creator is a German national, affiliated with an American university, and uploads their visuals from Switzerland, Swiss copyright law applies. This principle might also impact the decision on which research data repository to choose for the visuals. In this regard, knowledge about the legislation of the country in which the repository is placed is advantageous.

In these recommendations, we refer to the minimum standards provided by the Berne Convention, with the purpose of giving an international perspective of the legal aspects that must be considered when sharing visual research data. Researchers must then verify national applicable laws to understand the applicable details and requirements.

Question 2: Is the visual a protected work?

To be protected by copyright, in principle, visuals must satisfy three conditions, and the protection must still be valid (duration of protection). The three conditions are:

1) *Made by a human being:*

A visual work must be created by a human being to qualify for copyright protection. Works produced by machines or animals are not eligible. For instance, surveillance camera footage is not considered an intellectual creation because it records events automatically, without human input. Also, radar photos are taken automatically and are not protected by copyright. Consequently, also visuals fully created by GenAI are currently not protected by copyright. However, if a person modifies a GenAI-created visual, copyright protection may apply, at least to the parts added/modified by the person. It is always good practice to mention if GenAI has been used in the creation or editing of a visual.

2) *Perceivable to the senses (readable, listenable, touchable, watchable)*

Visuals generally satisfy this condition, as they can be seen or watched by other people.

3) *Original*

Originality is probably the most challenging criteria, as it is not always easy to determine when something qualifies as original in terms of copyright law. It must be assessed on a case-by-case basis. A helpful way to recognize originality is to ask whether someone else could create the exact same visual. If the answer is no, the work is likely original enough. For example, filming while walking without focusing on any specific object, composition, light exposure etc., does not result in a video protected by copyright, as anyone walking along the same path would likely produce a very similar video. Some countries also provide copyright protection to simple and banal photographs lacking originality.

There are two special types of works that are important to consider: *Collection of images*, that is a dataset composed of different visuals. This collection may itself be protected by copyright, if the way in which the visuals are selected and organized is original (e.g., sets of images published in an archive with a specific selection and arrangement); 2) *Derivative works*, that is modified visuals that are protected by copyright as new works if the modifications have been made by a person and have originality (e.g., a translated video recording).

To make sure that a visual is still protected, it is fundamental to consider the *duration of copyright protection*. Copyright protection is in fact limited to a certain time after which the work enters the “public domain” (all works to which copyright no longer applies). At this point, previous right holders no longer have exclusive rights to the work, and the work can be used freely without having to ask for consent. The Berne Convention requires signatory countries to provide copyright protection for at least the entire lifetime of the author, plus 50 years from the author’s death. In the case of works of applied art and photographic works lacking originality, the minimum term is 25 years from the creation of the work. National laws are free to apply longer terms of protection. For example, in Europe, the protection generally ends 70 years after the author’s death.

Question 3: Do you have permission to share?

To answer this question, it is important to understand several key concepts, such as who holds the rights to a work, what the implications of that role are, and what it means to have permission to use a work, which is typically granted through a license.

In a first step, researchers need to understand whether they are the authors and/or rights holders of the visuals they want to share. The *rights holder* is the individual or entity that holds the legal rights to control how visual materials may be used and exploited. This includes the rights to reproduce, distribute, modify, or display the visuals in specific contexts. When a visual work has multiple co-rights holders, any further use of the visuals must be approved collectively by all of them.

The *author (or the authors* in the case of a collaborative visual work) is typically the rights holder. However, authors often transfer some or all of their rights to another party, such as an employer, university, or institution, either through a contract (e.g., an employment or partnership contract) or by law. For example, depending on the applicable agreements or legal provisions, the affiliated university may hold the rights to visual research data created by its researchers. In the absence of such an agreement or legal transfer, the author(s) retain the rights to their data.

If researchers wish to share other people’s visual data under a Creative Commons license, they must obtain explicit authorization from the rights holder. Without such permission, they are not allowed to apply a Creative Commons license to the visual material used.

If the researcher is not the rights holder, it is important to first verify whether the visuals in question have been *released under a license that permits re-sharing*. This is often the case with Creative Commons licenses, particularly the open licenses, such as CC0, CC BY, or CC BY-SA. However, even more restrictive licenses, whether Creative Commons or others (e.g., platform-specific terms for sharing visuals), may allow re-sharing under certain conditions. The terms of any license should be carefully reviewed to understand what uses are permitted. For example, some licenses may require attribution or limit sharing to non-commercial or research-only purposes. These conditions determine the extent to which the visuals can be shared and thus the degree of openness that is possible.

If the visuals in question have not been released under a license that allows re-sharing, *explicit permission* must be obtained from the rights holder before any sharing can occur. Without such permission, limited use of the visuals may be permitted by copyright exceptions, but sharing them in a repository is not allowed. Such a permission or agreement can be either oral or written; though a written record, such as an email, is strongly recommended to prevent future disputes.

If obtaining permission is not possible, due to an unknown rights holder or a refusal, sharing the visuals is not permitted. In such cases, it is advisable to consult the relevant legal framework and the competent national Collective Management Organization – CMO (also called Collecting Societies), administering the rights of copyright holders, to explore any available options for sharing works with unknown rights holders. Additionally, the terms of a personalized license will determine the degree of openness under which the visuals may be shared.

Sometimes it is difficult or even impossible to identify the photographer of an image. Press photographs, for example, are sometimes credited to the publisher rather than the individual

author. In this case, researchers can contact the copyright holder, who most likely is the press editor, and request permission to use the image. They should pay attention to obtain explicit consent to include the images in their research dataset and to publish them under an open license. Also, clearly indicate the attribution it prefers next to each corresponding image. If it is not possible to determine the photographer's name, label the image as "Author unknown." Collective Management Organizations might also be able to support the researchers in finding the author or the rights holder, or grant the required permission to use visuals.

4.4.3. Licenses

When researchers retain copyright over their visual data, it is essential, and often required by funders, to specify whether, and under which conditions, such materials may be reused by others. Licensing serves as the mechanism to provide legal clarity and to facilitate responsible reuse. Creative Commons licenses offer a standardized and widely adopted framework that allows researchers to communicate usage rights without the need to draft custom legal agreements. Given their global recognition and legal interoperability, these licenses are particularly well-suited to the transnational nature of open science, promoting both transparency and accessibility in scholarly communication. However, in certain cases, standardized licenses may not adequately address specific needs, such as privacy concerns or ethical obligations, and the use of tailored, project-specific licenses may be necessary. The following section provides an overview of different types of licenses and the options they offer. These licensing choices are key factors in determining the appropriate level of openness for sharing data (see section 5).

However, these licenses apply only to *copyright* and *do not override data protection* regulations. When researchers publish data under a Creative Commons license, it is generally assumed that either no personal data are included, informed consent for data sharing has been obtained from the individuals concerned, or, though rarely, a prevailing public interest justifies the disclosure. While all Creative Commons licenses allow for reuse, they differ in the scope and conditions of the permissions they grant.

Three Creative Commons licenses (CC0, CC BY, and CC BY-SA) are fully aligned with the Open Definition (Open Knowledge Foundation, n.d.c), as they permit reuse of the work for any purpose. The remaining Creative Commons licenses impose certain restrictions, such as limiting reuse to non-commercial purposes or prohibiting the distribution of modified versions (non-derivatives).

When visuals are released under a CC0 license, anyone is free to reshare and modify them without restrictions. According to Creative Commons (n.d.a), attribution is not legally required under the CC0 license, although good scientific practice encourages acknowledging the author(s) and source.

The CC BY license permits anyone to share the content, provided that the author, title, source, and license itself are clearly acknowledged. If you modify visuals under this license, you are free to distribute your modified versions under any license, including those that are not open. The full terms of this license are described in Creative Commons (n.d.b)

The CC BY-SA license allows anyone to share the content for any purpose, as long as the author, title, source, and license are properly credited. In addition, any modifications must be distributed under the same CC BY-SA license. The full terms of this license are described in Creative Commons (n.d.c).

Creative Commons licenses that include the *ND* (NoDerivatives) element do not allow the sharing of modified versions of the content; visuals may only be distributed in their original, unaltered form. This includes a ban on cropping images for thumbnails and social media previews.

Licenses containing the *NC* (NonCommercial) element prohibit the use of the content in any context that involves economic gain, meaning the visuals cannot be used for commercial purposes.

Creative Commons licenses can only be applied if the visuals are published without access restrictions, meaning they must be freely accessible to everyone. If this is not the case, such as when visuals are made available exclusively to researchers, *personalized or custom licenses* should be used instead.

These personalized licenses can specify which categories of users are permitted to access and share the visuals, for which purposes, and whether modifications are allowed. In situations where access is granted only upon request, i.e., access is highly restricted, bilateral personalized licenses may be appropriate. In such cases, it is typically not necessary to define user groups, as permissions are granted on an individual basis. Personalized licenses are also suitable when more restrictive terms than those allowed by Creative Commons licenses are required. These are then considered more restrictive licenses.

More information on copyright, particularly in the Swiss context, is available on the CCdigitallaw platform (Competence Center in Digital Law, n.d.). Its knowledge base explains the fundamentals of copyright in an accessible language, supported by examples and FAQs. Additionally, the DMLaw Tool (Competence Center in Digital Law, 2021) offers a decision tree to help researchers in the humanities and social sciences navigate key legal issues in research data management, proposing practical solutions for copyright and data protection challenges. These solutions can also be applied to visual research data.

5. Degrees of openness for visual open data practices

Key take-aways

Degrees of openness can be:

- *Fully open data*, allowing unrestricted reuse with attribution under Creative Commons licenses.
- *Intermediate levels of openness*, accessible and reusable with conditions such as creator approval, restricted access to certain groups, or use limited to specific purposes.
- *Fully closed data*, where data cannot be shared at all, though metadata should still be provided in line with FAIR principles.

Two dimensions of openness:

- *Permitted access*: Who can view the data? Options range from everyone, specific categories, access upon request and no access.

Permitted reuse: What can users do with the data? Options differ with respect to editing options and re-use purposes.

Licensing and guidelines for future use:

- *Creative Commons licenses* apply only when access is open to all.
- *More restrictive or personalized licenses* can specify user groups, permitted purposes, and editing limitations.
- *Beyond formal licenses*, researchers are encouraged to provide guidelines for future data use that explain the original research aims, ethical challenges, consent details, and appropriate or inappropriate forms of reuse.

Which visuals to publish and how to alter them:

- Researchers must decide, case by case, whether to publish visuals openly, restrict them, or adapt them. Decisions should consider the continued research value of modified images, ethical implications, and the research paradigm. Ideally, each visual should be evaluated individually, though current repository infrastructures often force uniform publication conditions for entire datasets.

The aim of this section is to provide researchers with a range of options for determining the appropriate level of openness when publishing visual research data. In line with the spirit of open science, the guiding principle should be: *as open as possible, as restricted as necessary*. Researchers must strike a balance between the benefits of open science, such as verifiability, reproducibility, and accessibility, and the rights and well-being of the people involved, intellectual property holders, and ethical responsibilities. The decision regarding the degree of openness should be made only after a careful evaluation of all the considerations outlined in chapter two of these recommendations, which include, e.g., adequate anonymization, consent, selection of visuals that can be shared, and eventual substitutes (such as verbal descriptions).

5.1. Degrees of openness

Once these considerations are concluded, researchers can share their data at varying levels of openness, depending on the circumstances and ethical and legal implications.

At the most open end of the spectrum, *fully open data* are made freely available under open licenses, such as the Creative Commons CC BY license, which allows unrestricted reuse, including modifications and adaptations, provided that proper attribution is given to the data (ideally: author's name, work's title, source, and license).

Below this most open model, there are several *intermediate levels of openness*. These levels vary in their usage terms and conditions, ranging from minor requirements like approval from the dataset creator to more restrictive agreements that protect sensitive or proprietary information. In the most restrictive case, data cannot be shared at all, typically due to privacy concerns, intellectual property barriers, or other contractual obligations, but comprehensive metadata can still be made available. This complies with the *accessibility* requirement of the FAIR principles and ensures that other researchers are aware of the dataset's existence and can request access under specific agreements. Territorial limits may also influence data accessibility: for example, personal data might be approved for use and storage only within a certain country, preventing publication on global or foreign repositories.

Restricted access data may be shared under personalized conditions that regulate who can use the data (e.g., anyone, or only researchers within the same institution) and how it can be used (in compliance with the *reusability* condition of the FAIR principles). These conditions may be outlined in custom "personalized" usage agreements tailored to the dataset's nature or sensitivity. In some cases, only parts of a dataset may be shareable, while others remain restricted.

Choosing the appropriate level of openness ensures a balance between transparency, reusability, and responsibility. Data should be published with adequate terms and conditions that are in line with ethical and legal considerations.

5.2. Two dimensions of openness: permitted access and usage

There are two dimensions that can be used for determining the openness of visual data: 1) define who can access them (*permitted access*) and 2) define what people having access to visuals can do with them (*permitted usage*). The degrees of openness of visual data thus results from the combination of "permitted access" and "permitted usage", as shown in Table 1.

Dimension 1: Permitted Access

Researchers can define the level of access they want to grant to their visual research data. This determines who can view the visuals. There are three levels of accessibility plus one, which is no-access; they are explained here below from the most open to the most restrictive.

Everyone has access / can view the archived images: To do so, the visuals are ideally archived in an open research data repository following the FAIR principles. In this, and only this case, Creative Commons licenses can be used.

One or more categories of users have access or can view the archived visuals: Access can, for example, be limited to researchers in general, to researchers or members of a single Higher Education Institution, to users of a specific country, or to those paying for access to the repository on which the visuals are stored. This can be achieved by selecting specific repositories (e.g., an institutional repository) or by limiting access to the visuals on the research data repository to specific groups of people that can be automatically recognized through authentication procedures on the repository.

Access upon request: Access is granted upon specific request and can be evaluated by the researcher or research institution on a case-by-case basis. This allows even more control over

access to research visual data. Also, in this case, the visuals might be stored in a repository, but without providing general access.

No access at all: This cannot truly be considered a level of access, as it completely prevents any use of the visual materials; no visuals are shared. However, it is recommended to at least provide metadata describing the visuals, so that others are aware of their existence and the potential relevance of the research data.

		ACCESS			
		Everyone	Category	On request	No
REUSE	All purposes with edits	Fully Open: Licenses: CC0, CC BY, CC BY-SA Public Domain	Limited access; Reuse for all purposes; With edits Licenses: Personalized license with category specification	Very Limited Access; Reuse for all purposes; With edits Licenses: bilateral personalized license	Fully closed
	All purposes no edits	Full Access, Reuse for all purposes; No Edits Licenses: CC BY-ND or personalized license with editing limitation	Limited Access; Reuse for all purposes; No Edits Licenses: personalized license with category specification and editing limitation	Very Limited Access; Reuse for all purposes; No Edits Licenses: bilateral personalized license with editing limitation	Fully closed
	Limited purposes with edits	Full Access, Reuse for limited purposes, With Edits Licenses: CC BY-NC, CC BY-NC-SA (for granting non-commercial use), or personalized license with purpose limitation	Limited Access, Reuse for limited purposes, With Edits Licenses: personalized license with category specification and purpose limitation	Very Limited Access, Reuse for limited purposes, With Edits Licenses: bilateral personalized license with purpose limitation	Fully closed
	Limited purposes no edits	Full Access, Reuse for limited purposes, No Edits Licenses: CC BY-NC-ND, (for granting non-commercial use), or personalized license with purpose and editing limitation	Limited Access, Reuse for limited purposes, No Edits Licenses: personalized license with category specification and purpose and editing limitation	Very Limited Access, Reuse for limited purposes, No Edits Licenses: bilateral personalized license with purpose and editing limitation	Fully closed
	No	Full Access, No Reuse	Limited Access, No Reuse	Very Limited Access, No Reuse	Fully closed

Table 1 - Degrees of Openness

Dimension 2: Permitted Usage / Reuse

Researchers can clearly define what people who have access to the visual data can do with it. The variable is composed of two components: 1) the so-called *purpose for reuse* and 2) whether *edits/modifications are allowed*. Based on this, it is possible to permit some forms of reuse and prevent others (e.g., whether used for research, commercial, or non-commercial purposes). What is allowed to be done with an image is defined through specific, “personalized” licenses or predefined and non-modifiable licenses, such as Creative Commons Licenses. Beware that Creative Commons Licenses can only be used if the permitted access has not been limited, as they only apply if access is open to everyone. Depending on the permitted usage and the accessibility level, personalized licenses might include purpose and editing limitations and specify the user categories for having access. In case of very limited access, so-called bilateral personal licenses can be used, which work the same way as personalized licenses, but due to the nature of bilateral agreements, they do not need to specify user categories. These aspects can be specified in short sentences. Licenses must be carefully chosen or defined at the time of publication. There are five categories of permitted usage levels, described below in order from the most open to the most restrictive.

Reuse for any purpose also with modifications (edits): In this case, everyone who has access to the images can reuse them for any kind of purpose and is even allowed to edit them. This also includes commercial usage.

Possible licenses are:

- *Public Domain*, in case the visuals are not protected by copyright
- *CC0*, if any usage is allowed under no conditions (to keep in mind that moral rights remain protected)
- *CC BY*, if the only condition is to mention the author of the images
- *CC BY-SA*, in case you want users to share the modified visuals under the same CC BY-SA license

CC0, CC BY, and CC BY-SA are the only Creative Commons licenses considered “open”. They can only be used if access is granted to everyone; otherwise, personalized or bilateral licenses have to be established.

Reuse for any purpose but without modifications (edits): In this case, everyone who has access to the visual data can reuse them for any kind of purpose, but is not allowed to edit them. This means that people must use the dataset or the single data exactly as they have been shared. If the visual has been shared as part of a dataset, it means that only the entire dataset can be reused and not the single visuals composing it, as this would already be a modification to the entire dataset, and the user would extract the single visual from its original context.

Possible licenses are:

- Personalized or bilateral personalized licenses specifying the purpose of reuse and editing limitation
- *CC BY-ND* (allows a dataset or a visual to be reused but does not allow the publication of derivatives/modifications) – can only be used if access is granted to everyone

Reuse for limited purposes also with modifications: In this case, researchers can define for which purposes the visuals can be reused. Reuse can, for example, be limited to non-commercial or research-only activities. Modification of visuals is still possible in this case. For example, they can change a color image to black and white, or they can add, modify, or translate text visible on the visuals, or they can use only one or a few visuals from an entire dataset.

Possible licenses are:

- Personalized or bilateral personalized licenses specifying the purpose of reuse (e.g., research activities)
- *CC BY-NC* or *CC BY-NC-SA* if the purpose shall be restricted to non-commercial use – can only be used if access is granted to everyone

Reuse for limited purposes without modifications: In this case, researchers can limit the purpose of reuse without allowing modifications to the visuals. This means that visual data must be reused exactly in the way they have been shared.

Possible licenses are:

- Personalized or bilateral personalized licenses specifying the purpose of reuse and editing limitations (no modifications are allowed)
- *CC BY-NC-ND*, which restricts the purpose of use to non-commercial use and does not allow the creation of derivatives (modifications) – can only be used if access is granted to everyone

No re-use allowed: In this case, the reuse of visuals is not permitted in any form.

Beware that legal copyright exceptions such as private use, educational purposes, and text and data mining still apply, regardless of any license terms.

In addition to selecting an appropriate license, which defines the legal conditions for data reuse, researchers should be encouraged to develop and share *written guidelines for future data use*. While licenses clarify the formal terms under which data can be reused, they often do not capture the ethical, contextual, or methodological boundaries that are critical for responsible use, particularly in the case of visual data. We thus suggest that guidelines for future data use should accompany datasets and serve as a narrative, ethically informed document. They can include important contextual information such as the aims of the original research, reflections on ethical challenges, details about consent, and any sensitivities around identifiability or cultural representation. Most importantly, researchers should clearly specify which types of future uses they deem appropriate based on the knowledge of the research context, under what conditions, and which uses should be avoided, even if this is not legally restricted. This practice supports transparency, promotes ethical reuse, and helps guide secondary users in maintaining the integrity of the original research. It also emphasizes the responsibility of future users, encouraging them to move beyond simply “taking and using” the data and instead to engage with it critically and contextually. While such guidelines cannot legally enforce compliance, they represent a valuable tool for fostering ethical accountability in open data practices and should be actively supported by institutions and repositories.

5.3. Which visuals to publish and how much to alter them?

If you are the copyright holder, or if you have obtained permission from the rights holder, you may adapt or edit individual visuals so that they can be shared as openly as possible, for example, by blurring faces or covering sensitive areas (however, see section 4.3.3. on anonymization and 4.3.2. on consent).

Deciding whether to share an image in a less open manner or to modify it for wider accessibility depends on several factors, including the continued relevance of the visual after modification, the effort and resources required to make the changes, and considerations related to research ethics and the research paradigm (see section 4). Such decisions should be made on a case-by-case basis.

Ideally, all these considerations, including the choice of degree of openness, should be considered for each single visual data item that is part of the overall visual research data of a research project. This enables to decide whether to publish the entire dataset under the same conditions, to divide it into groups with uniform publication terms, or to publish visuals individually.

At present, certain limitations regarding the desired choice of degrees of openness prevail, as many research data repositories only allow for a single dataset to be uploaded per project. This constraint often forces researchers to apply a single level of openness to all visuals in a dataset. However, it is hoped that these practices will evolve in the coming years to support more flexible sharing models.

6. Conclusions

The recommendations presented in this document underscore the importance of carefully considering the ethical, legal, and practical complexities involved in sharing visual research data in the context of visual social research within open science frameworks. Visual data, with its high density of visual cues, the difficulty of guaranteeing anonymity to depicted people, and their contextual sensitivity, poses unique challenges that cannot be fully addressed through generic open data guidelines. Instead, decisions about openness must be made with respect to research paradigms, participant rights, and the specificities of each visual element.

By outlining key considerations across the entire research lifecycle, from consent and anonymization to licensing and repository selection, these recommendations support a nuanced, responsible, and reflexive approach to visual open data practices. The proposed

framework encourages researchers to strive for transparency and accessibility while ensuring respect for participants and safeguarding against harm.

Importantly, these recommendations advocate for *degrees of openness* rather than binary choices, promoting flexible strategies tailored to ethical and legal contexts. They aim to empower researchers, and help ethics boards, and institutions in making informed decisions that align with both the goals of open science and the values of research ethic and responsibility.

We argue that, additionally, sharing clearly formulated *guidelines for future data use* alongside the visual data is an important and constructive step toward responsible data sharing. These guidelines can serve as an accompanying document that supports ethical reuse by offering future users essential contextual information, such as the original research aims, ethical reflections by the researchers, details about participant consent, and the social or cultural contexts and sensitivities of the visual material. Crucially, researchers can use this document to clearly articulate which forms of future use are considered adequate and under what specific conditions. This goes beyond what legal licensing frameworks typically provide, as such licenses often do not capture the full ethical nuance of visual data. By providing this form of narrative or reflective metadata, the guidelines function as a moral and methodological compass for secondary users, encouraging practices that respect both the participants and the original research context. However, even with such documentation, there remains uncertainty about how intended uses can be guaranteed or monitored in fully open data environments. Without mechanisms for tracking or enforcing these conditions, there is a risk of ethical misuse or misinterpretation. Hence, Institutional Review Boards should also evaluate whether secondary studies respect the conditions of the original research when reusing data. These challenges and uncertainties underline the need for both institutional support and technical innovation to ensure that open data practices remain not only legally compliant but also ethically robust, particularly in the case of sensitive or visual data.

While we have presented several key challenges in these recommendations, at least three aspects need further considerations and reflections in the future:

1) *AI and the reuse of open data*: In fact, with the rapid advancement of artificial intelligence, especially generative models capable of harvesting and reprocessing large volumes of visual data, new ethical dilemmas are emerging. Concerns about unintended reuse, decontextualization, or algorithmic bias underscore the need for continuous monitoring of how repository data may be used by AI systems in the future. Addressing these risks requires updated consent practices, clearer licensing, and possibly new technical safeguards.

2) *Global equity in open data access*: As open science aspires to be truly inclusive and collaborative, efforts are needed to ensure equitable access and participation, especially for researchers and communities in the Global South. Disparities in technological infrastructure, legal systems, and institutional support can limit meaningful engagement. Responsible open data practices must recognize these imbalances and work towards redistributive justice in both access and contributions to global scientific knowledge.

3) *Choice of “visual” repository*: Clear guidelines and targeted support are essential to help researchers choose appropriate repositories for their data, particularly when dealing with visual data. While in the annex we have outlined several criteria for evaluating repositories and navigating the growing landscape of open data platforms, a critical gap remains: there is currently a lack of specific guidance on how to identify repositories that are well-suited for storing, sharing, and preserving visual data in an adequate way. This typically means allowing for metadata on the level of single items and allowing for contextual information to be shared. Visual data can take many forms, ranging from photographs and video recordings to maps, data visualizations, and other multimodal formats. These diverse data types come with unique requirements for metadata, annotation systems, file format compatibility, rights management, and ethical use. However, most repository interfaces are not explicitly designed to accommodate the particularities of visual research data. As a result, researchers often face a trial-and-error process when attempting to determine whether a given repository supports their

needs. Key functionalities, such as support for large file sizes, interactive previews, or layered access controls, are not always clearly communicated or easy to locate. As Hansson and Dahlgren (2022) point out, many repositories offer only limited metadata options at the level of individual images, making it difficult to accurately describe, discover, or reuse visual material. More comprehensive metadata tends to be available only at the level of the dataset as a whole. This reflects an underlying design assumption that treats research data as aggregated and homogeneous, a view that is fundamentally at odds with the situated and specific nature of visual data in many humanities and social science contexts. This situation highlights the urgent need for repositories to evolve in ways that better accommodate the complexities of visual research data, and for institutions and funders to provide clearer guidance and tailored support to researchers in this area.

Ultimately, these recommendations mark an important step toward shaping a responsible, context-sensitive culture of open visual research. They are intended not as a final word but as a foundation for continued dialogue, adaptation, and community-driven development in an evolving research landscape.

7. Annex – Open Data Tools

7.1. Data Management Plan

A Data Management Plan (DMP) is an important tool that allows researchers to reflect on and plan the entire life cycle of their research data. Essentially, a DMP is a “document that describes how you will treat your data during a project and what happens with the data after the project ends” (Michener, 2015). Ideally, the data management plan should already be developed in the planning phase of the research project, and thus long before the start of the project. A DMP is not considered static and should be validated and updated during the whole course of the research project to address new needs and issues. At the end of the project, a final version should be provided.

The DMP makes these considerations explicit and guides researchers throughout all stages of the research process. It also serves as a shared reference for everyone involved (e.g., members of research teams that might change over time), outlining how data should be handled at each phase. By demonstrating that ethical and procedural aspects have been thoughtfully addressed from the outset, the DMP helps build trust with participants. Additionally, it acts as a practical tool to ensure that researchers do not overlook important steps, any of which, if neglected, could hinder the proper archiving and sharing of data or result in disrespectful practices. The DMP is always based on ethical principles and allows researchers to plan what kind of consents to request and how, when collecting data, which amounts of resources to allocate to the preparation of data for archiving and publication (e.g., creation of metadata, anonymization), and thus to guarantee that data will be archived and shared in a respectful and transparent way.

Many public research funding organizations, such as the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF), or the European Commission, nowadays require a DMP for research projects before releasing funds. Even though emphasis is put on sharing data openly whenever possible, there are reasonable exceptions. As we have discussed above, archiving and sharing visual data openly yields a variety of challenges, and is often not compatible with open data practices. Hence, funding institutions acknowledge that “some data cannot be shared because grantees are bound to legal, ethical, copyright, confidentiality or other clauses.” (SNSF, n.d.) And even FAIR Data Principles do not force researchers to openly share all their data without restrictions.

In this context, the DMP provides researchers with a space to explain whether their visual data can be archived and shared, and if so, to what extent. Clearly stating these decisions from the beginning, in a transparent manner, helps to prevent misunderstandings, unrealistic expectations, or concerns later in the project. For funding bodies, it is essential that any limitations are clearly explained. A DMP should therefore be seen as a supportive and practical tool that facilitates the research process, rather than as a mere administrative requirement for obtaining funding.

Different funding agencies and higher education institutions provide their own guidelines and templates for DMPs reflecting their priorities. The Swiss National Science Foundation, for example, has defined minimum standards for the structure and content of the information that needs to be provided in order to account for different data management practices between disciplines (SNSF, n.d.). Michener (2015) presents ten simple rules that can help create a good and effective DMP. Particularly relevant for the context of these recommendations are rule 4: explain how the data will be documented, rule 6: present a sound data storage and preservation strategy, rule 7: define the project’s data policies, and rule 8: describe how the data will be disseminated.

Furthermore, a data management checklist that can be easily adapted to the requirements of different funding organizations is provided by DLCM, the Research Data Management Hub (DLCM, 2018), which is divided by topics and stages of the data life cycle and points out a variety of relevant questions that should be addressed in a DMP.

Furthermore, it is important to consider that funding agencies might cover the costs for preparing research data for their archiving in a non-commercial data repository that is compliant with FAIR data principles. However, these costs must be taken into account at the time of the submission of the research proposal.

7.2. Consent Form

In visual social research, informed consent is a foundational ethical obligation that protects participants' autonomy and dignity (see section 4.3.2.). Far from being a one-time formality, consent should be understood as a dynamic, iterative, and context-sensitive process that in some research traditions, should be revisited at key stages, e.g., before image creation, during analysis, and prior to public dissemination. Given the potentially identifiable nature of visual data, traditional assurances of anonymity and confidentiality often fall short. Wiles et al. (2008) therefore emphasize the need for flexible and ongoing consent, allowing participants to retain agency over how their images are used throughout the research lifecycle. It is important to note that obtaining informed consent should protect participants. The consent forms should not be seen as a mere "contract" (Pauwels, 2008) that protects researchers.

The consent form plays a crucial role in visual social research. It is typically a written agreement that informs participants about the study's purpose and nature while explicitly authorizing the use of their visual data. With respect to the use of visuals in open data practices, consent forms must also address issues of visibility, identifiability, and the potential future use or dissemination of images, along with the associated risks and implications. In other words, participants should ideally be involved in discussions of anonymization and the use of single visuals.

As noted above, consent must be *truly informed*. Researchers should clearly communicate the aims of the study, the intended uses of visual materials, and potential emotional, reputational, or cultural impacts, enabling participants to make well-informed decisions. As this is a complex task, enough time and consideration need to be invested when setting up consent procedures and creating the written consent forms. As argued above, research participants are typically not familiar with scientific procedures and might be unaware of open data practices and the role of repositories. In order to make informed decisions, they need to understand what happens to their data after the research is concluded. Consent procedures might even need to be adapted to address the specific needs and vulnerabilities of groups such as minors, individuals with cognitive disabilities, or participants from diverse cultural backgrounds (Heath et al., 2007; Pink, 2013). In contexts where literacy is limited or where written forms might cause mistrust, alternative formats such as video or audio recordings can be especially suitable (Banks, 2001).

Prieto-Blanco (2021) and Wiles et al. (2008) emphasize the importance of *modular consent*, which allows participants to agree to certain aspects of a study, such as being interviewed, while declining others, such as the use of images in publications or data repositories. Ideally, consented potential future uses should be discussed individually for each visual item, as participants may view some visuals as more sensitive than others. As a result, consent forms should be designed with sufficient complexity to accommodate these distinctions, rather than relying on a single, all-encompassing consent checkbox.

These approaches emphasize the importance of transparency, flexibility, and respect in the ethical design and application of consent forms in visual social research. In general, participants should be meaningfully involved in decisions about how their images are used throughout the entire data lifecycle.

7.3. Choice of Repository

A data repository is a digital platform designed to store, preserve, and share research data in ways that support transparency, reuse, and long-term access. When working with visual data, special considerations must be made to ensure ethical, legal, and technical suitability. The following criteria help assess whether a repository is appropriate for depositing visual data:

Type of repository: It is necessary to assess whether the repository is *generic* (such as Zenodo or OSF) or tailored to a specific *discipline*. Repositories familiar with handling large visual and multimodal files and rich metadata may be better suited for visual data. It should also be examined whether the repository aligns with the specific requirements of visual social research within the chosen research paradigm.

Compliance with FAIR principles: The repository should ideally support *Findability* (e.g., with DOIs), *Accessibility* (e.g., access conditions and metadata), *Interoperability* (e.g., standard file formats and metadata structures), and *Reusability* (e.g., documentation, data usage license). For visual data, reusability may also include clear usage restrictions or consent-based access conditions, where needed.

Versioning and updates: Repositories used for visual data should allow version control, enabling updates to datasets (e.g., improved metadata, additional consent clarifications, redactions) while maintaining a clear record of previous versions. This is especially important when managing participant consent over time.

Cost and access fees: While some repositories are free to use, others charge for data uploads or long-term storage. Many impose file size limits or require payment for deposits that exceed a certain threshold. This is particularly relevant for visual social research, which often produces large, multimodal files such as high-resolution images or videos. Researchers should therefore plan for potential storage costs in their project budgets and also consider whether access to the data will remain free for end users.

Who can deposit and access data: It is important to clarify whether any researcher is permitted to upload data, or if deposits are restricted to individuals affiliated with certain institutions. Consideration should also be given to who is allowed to view or download the data, particularly when dealing with visual materials that may raise ethical concerns, such as those involving internal confidentiality or culturally sensitive content.

Compliance with the demands of funding organizations and institutions: Researchers should ensure that the chosen repository meets the specific requirements set by funding bodies and affiliated institutions. These may include adherence to open access mandates, data preservation standards, licensing expectations, and alignment with the FAIR principles. Demonstrating such compliance is often essential for fulfilling grant conditions and institutional research data policies.

Suitability for visual data: Finally, and most importantly, it is essential to assess whether the repository is technically and ethically equipped to handle the respective visual data. This includes support for large datasets, heavy files, high-resolution file formats (e.g., .jpg, .tiff, .mp4), ideally metadata fields specific to visual content, preview capabilities, and access control features where needed. The ideal repository should accommodate the complexity and specificity of visual data rather than treat it as generic or homogeneous. These requirements are, unfortunately, still not fulfilled by most repositories (see Branney et al. 2019; Prosser). Repositories that allow the inclusion of contextual and ethical documentation, such as consent frameworks or usage guidelines, are particularly important for supporting responsible visual data sharing.

8. Author Biographies

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Anna Picco-Schwendener, PhD, is a researcher at the Institute of Digital Technologies for Communication at the Faculty of Communication, Culture and Society of the Università della Svizzera italiana (USI), where she teaches Online Communication Design and E-Government. She also leads USI's Competence Centre in Digital Law (www.ccdigitallaw.ch), a national center that supports Swiss higher education institutions in addressing legal issues related to the digitization process and the use of new media and technologies. With a focus on prevention, the Centre aims to make legal content, especially in the areas of copyright, data protection, privacy, and licensing, accessible to non-legal experts. With a background in communication science, she focuses on improving the communication of legal knowledge in research and education. She coordinates legal aspects of several national projects in the field of Open Science, especially in the social sciences and humanities, with a focus on Open Access and Open Research Data.

Suzanna Farace Marazza is a jurist and legal consultant at CCdigitallaw (USI's eLearning Lab), where she advises on digital law issues such as copyright, licensing, and data protection, especially in academia. She conducts multilingual workshops and supports Open Access projects. She is currently pursuing a PhD at the University of Neuchâtel, focusing on copyright, digitization, and AI in memory institutions. She holds certifications in intellectual property law from WIPO and Creative Commons, and has experience in public administration and legal internships in Switzerland and abroad. She also volunteers in the Creative Commons open culture community.

Pasqualina Sibio holds a Bachelor's degree in Communication from the Università della Svizzera italiana (USI). At eLab, she supports the design and promotion of digital skills training for USI students and staff, contributing to initiatives that enhance digital literacy across the university community. She wrote her thesis on privacy policies, focusing on how to make them more understandable and accessible to the public. As part of this work, she developed a prototype aimed at improving the usability of privacy policies for users, combining legal accuracy with clear, user-centered communication strategies. Within CCdigitallaw she contributes to workshops, to the communication and simplification of legal content, including the production of informational videos and the management of social media channels. In particular, she helps translate complex legal concepts into accessible content on topics such as copyright, data protection, open access, and open science, key areas of CCdigitallaw's expertise.

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